

THE PASTORAL COUNSELLORS

JOURNAL *of* **NIGERIAN ASSOCIATION OF PASTORAL COUNSELLORS**

In collaboration with
Department of Religious and Intercultural Studies
and
Department of Guidance and Counselling
LEAD CITY UNIVERSITY, IBADAN, NIGERIA

VOL. 3. MAY 2024

ISSN: PRINT 2971-5199 ONLINE 2971-5202

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Ethical Issues in Pastoral Counselling of Widows: A Critical Review

Oluwakemi Bolatito BABARINDE, PhD
Baptist College of Theology, Lagos, Nigeria
revkemibb@yahoo.com, +2348023198108

Abstract

Widowhood is a reality and consists of grief situations. Often, widows seek help from pastors and the church during these unpleasant experiences. To aid holistic healing, pastoral counselling, a unique and integral facet of spiritual care, is vital. However, some pastors often use these counselling processes to exploit widows financially, sexually, and emotionally, amongst others. These exploitations have necessitated a careful review of the ethical issues during the counselling of widows. Secondary data sources were used to understand widows' grief situations, the impact of pastoral counselling, and the ethical dimensions surrounding the counselling process, with some ethical pastoral cases presented. It was found that theological institutions, pastoral, and the church have a role in addressing the ethical dilemma surrounding pastoral counselling. It was recommended that theological institutions develop modules on counselling widows, churches implement specialised training programmes for pastoral counsellors, and clear policies should be developed with regular evaluations. Likewise, pastors should integrate some secular counselling approaches and collaborate with professional therapists when needed. The review concludes that pastoral counsellors can establish a foundation of trust and support for widows in their journey toward healing by acknowledging and addressing the unique challenges they face through an ethical lens.

Keywords: Ethical Issues, Grief, Pastoral Counselling, Widows, Widowhood

Introduction

Grief describes a normal response to the loss of a loved one or anything dear to one's heart. The most common cause of this form of loss is death. Death is inevitable. It strikes at any time. To cope with such a loss, counselling may be required. Counselling assists individuals, such as widows, with their concerns to positively adjust to the reality of the loss (Mburugu, 2020). In most cases, widows seek counsel from their religious leaders. If they are Christians, they consult their pastors (Wolfelt, 2003). A pastor is the spiritual leader of a Christian congregation. According to Odeleye (2022), pastors can be referred to by several titles, usually based on their roles, such as shepherd, nurturer, watchman, and carer. Pastors need to be equipped with a unique blend of spiritual insight and psychological understanding to play a pivotal role in facilitating healing and inspiring resilience in widows, especially through counselling.

Pastoral Counselling involves a counsellor, in this case, a pastor, being receptive to exploring the inner psychological dynamics of individuals. Such assistance is given while recognising the shared spiritual values that can be crucial when navigating crises or existential challenges (Iwajomo, 2019). Hence, the significance of pastoral counselling in addressing the multifaceted needs of widows cannot be overstated, as widows often face challenges beyond conventional psychological counselling, involving issues of faith, existential questioning, and re-establishing purpose. Pastoral counselling integrates this unique space, intertwining psychological principles with spiritual guidance to provide a holistic support system to people.

However, as with any form of counselling, pastoral counselling encounters ethical considerations that demand careful examination. The ethical dimensions of pastoral counselling have begun to gain increased attention in recent years, with pastors and theological scholars recognising the need for a nuanced understanding of how ethical principles apply in this context.

Consequently, this paper critically reviewed secondary data such as book, journals, and news articles to explore the ethical issues in pastoral counselling for widows. It aims to shed light on the ethical issues pastors delve into and the challenges they pose to the widows seeking their support and making contextual recommendations for pastors and churches.

The Widowhood Phase

A widow is a woman with or without children who has lost her husband through death and has not married again (Boaheng & Boahen, 2022). As a result, she enters into widowhood experiences. Widowhood is a phenomenon or condition a widow or widower undergoes after the death of a spouse. Widowhood experiences for a woman, irrespective of age at bereavement, has a wide array of destabilising effect on her emotional and psychological well-being that can lead to mental health issues, such as depression, anxiety, frustration and others (Nwaoba, Ajoku, & Uba, 2022).

The loss of a beloved is very draining emotionally. The person experiences shock, confusion, and disbelief from the day of loss. Hopes become shattered, aspirations dashed, and it appears the final end has come (Olateru-Olagbegi, 2012). Loneliness is also experienced, especially as a widow. Olateru-Olagbegi (2012: 29) mentions that “she usually sat on her balcony, gazing at nothing and expecting her husband to walk home and speak with her. She felt empty despite having family and loved ones around her.” This means that loss sometimes comes with the refusal to accept the new reality and status as a widow.

The death of a husband marks a new phase in a woman's life, and she is expected to undergo specific rights depending on her culture. According to Ayoola (2017), widows comprise about half of the adult female population in many African societies. For these African women, mourning rites are required; for some women, it involves shaving their hair, burning the clothes they wore at the time of the husband's demise, sleeping beside the deceased, or even drinking the water used to bath the deceased to prove their innocence regards their husband's death (Boaheng & Boahen, 2022). Widows often experience oppressive and dehumanising cultural practices (Damap, 2008). They grapple with numerous challenges, attempting to manage the responsibilities formerly shouldered by their deceased spouses, which frequently take a toll on them, particularly impacting their health.

The writer, from observations, discovers that the attitudes of the late husband's relations may not be satisfactory to the widow, particularly if she is still young and/or dependent on her spouse, who was very rich. The situation may be unpleasant if they are focused on acquiring the deceased's properties rather than the welfare of the widow and her children, if any (Olateru-Olagbegi, 2012). This makes financial problems rank highest in all the plights of many widows because survival needs must be attended to.

Widowhood represents a profound life transition often accompanied by grief, emotional turmoil, and various challenges that necessitate support. In this context, pastoral counselling emerges as a vital resource, providing spiritual and emotional guidance to widows navigating the complexities of loss. One major aspect of pastoral care is pastoral counselling. It is a healing

ministry of the religious community built on a connection between a family or individual and a pastor (or a pastoral team) with counselling skills (Lartey, 2003).

In a study by Mohammed (2022), all the interview respondents in the study identified multiple factors they relied on to cope and survive; one of the distinctive ways is Faith and Belief in God. All the widows identified their faith in God as the primary source of support in dealing with the loss of their spouse as well as enduring traumatic practices that some of them were put through.

Impact of Pastoral Counselling on Widows

Pastoral counselling has the potential to yield both positive and negative outcomes, profoundly influencing the well-being of widows. On the positive side, it serves as a transformative force, fostering emotional healing, offering invaluable support, and cultivating empowerment and resilience. However, the negative consequences of pastoral counselling may manifest when ethical lapses occur. These lapses can give rise to trust issues and, in more severe cases, contribute to psychological harm.

The ethical dimensions of counselling play a pivotal role in shaping the overall well-being of widows, underscoring the need for a conscientious and principled approach in pastoral care. It emphasises the responsibility of counsellors to uphold the highest ethical standards and to ensure that the therapeutic process is a source of positive transformation rather than unintended distress.

Ethical Frameworks and Challenges in Pastoral Counselling

From the foregoing, the great task of the church makes it more expedient for the church to have sound counselling strength for its members that would enable them to get adequate care as needed. However, as with any form of counselling, pastoral counselling encounters ethical considerations that demand careful examination. Ethics in counselling are concerned with human conduct and doing what is in the client's best interest. The most common ethical principles include confidentiality, informed consent, cultural sensitivity, and professional competence, which are the ethical concerns this paper hinges on.

Confidentiality and Consent Concerns

Christian counsellors must obtain and maintain client confidentiality to the fullest extent as allowed by the law, professional ethics and bodies, and the church (Babatunde, 2021). All personal information and the disclosures made during sessions must be kept secret and secure. Counsellors need to seek and get permission or consent from the clients before acting on their behalf (Babatunde, 2021). It should be documented for future purposes. However, it is important to balance confidentiality with mandatory reporting. This is usually done when the griever has done or is about to do something harmful to himself or a loved one.

Also, consent for biblical practices should be requested. Though the griever is a Christian, during the grieving process, they might be struggling with their faith in God and imposing faith-based counselling methods such as prayers and Bible reading might hinder the journey to recovery. However, communicating the purpose and scope of counselling can help to ensure the widow knows what to expect from the counselling sessions.

From the foregoing, pastors are discouraged from using the information shared confidently as a reference point during church services or sharing it with colleagues, church leaders or members during discussions. It amounts to betrayal. It is unethical.

Cultural Sensitivity

Counsellors need to recognise that widows come from varied cultural contexts, each with its own set of beliefs, practices, and norms regarding grief, loss, and coping mechanisms (Betancourt et al., 2003). For instance, different cultures may have distinct rituals, mourning periods, and expectations regarding expressing grief. A counsellor's ability to comprehend and respect these cultural nuances is crucial for establishing trust and rapport with widows. Also, cultural biases can inadvertently influence counselling approaches, potentially leading to misunderstandings or even exacerbating the emotional distress of widows (Sue & Sue, 2012). Counsellors should strive to be aware of their cultural biases and ensure their interventions are culturally sensitive and respectful.

Cultural sensitivity in pastoral counselling is a dynamic and evolving process that requires ongoing education and self-reflection. By understanding the diverse cultural backgrounds of widows and actively avoiding cultural biases, counsellors can create a therapeutic space that is affirming, respectful, and conducive to the well-being of widows during their grief journey. During the grieving period, pastors are usually contacted for assistance by the widows. However, some pastoral counsellors do not help resolve issues but worsen the situation as a result of ignoring cultural practices or not managing the conflict situation properly due to personal biases or incompetence which sometimes, they might be aware of.

Competence and Professional Boundaries

Christian counsellors should not aid or abet the practice of unlicensed, untrained, unqualified, or unethical counselling. Instead, they are to consult and/or refer to more competent superiors or colleagues when their counselling limits have been reached (Babatunde, 2021). This is because a referral is integral to the healing experiences of grievors seeking wholeness (Abioye, 2021). It is important to note that referrals have a theological basis, which Abioye (2021) clearly expressed.

Usually, grievors, in this case, widows, need mature minds they can lean on for support and strength, and pastors fit in better to stand beside them. This type of service has been identified as ministry of presence. This usually provides succour and assurance of not being alone during grief, and widows can feel fulfilled, comforted and strengthened (Iwajomo, 2019). However, pastors need to maintain appropriate boundaries in the pastoral counselling relationship. In offering pastoral care and counselling, visitation, amongst many others, is a vital index because they need companionship and advice (Ayoola, 2017). If the visit is done, it should be with one's spouse or a partner or done in an open space to prevent suspicions or sexual temptations.

Professional boundaries can also be challenging, as avoiding such connections is crucial, especially when discussing sensitive topics that may lead to intense emotional bonds. This is why counsellors are advised to avoid providing therapy to family, friends, or individuals they have personal connections with, including relatives or acquaintances. These ethical boundaries aim to ensure impartial and confidential therapy for all clients, enabling them to express their issues freely. Because counselling means consultation, discussion, deliberation, exchange of ideas, advice or decision-making (Oyedele, 2017), some pastoral counsellors tend to enforce decisions on widows due to the power dynamics in the pastor-widow relationship. This is because widows tend to go along with the pastor's decisions.

Cumulative Integrity

This implies soundness, adherence to principle, and completeness in the sense of being undivided. Babatunde (2021) further explains that integrity can be seen as faithfulness to the Lord, regard to the Scripture, integrity of role and with the congregation, and within the limits of pastoral training.

According to Ayandokun (2021), those who engage in pastoral counselling should be persons of integrity who can be trusted and dependable without any trait of deception and manipulation of the client. The scholar adds that those helping bring healing and restoration to the griever should not add to their calamities. Hence, the pastor's morality and the counselling process's integrity must be maintained.

Ethical Pastoral Cases

As background to recommendations being made, selected case studies are presented below: According to Ologbosere (2018), a 59-year-old man allegedly defrauded a widow of N3 million. The man conspired with a friend, an alleged international fraudster, who presented himself as a pastor and convinced the woman that she was dealing with a credible Nigerian. The widow then gave them the amount to help her purchase two fairly used jeeps, but they made away with the money and extorted more from the widow under the pretext of paying duties on the car they never bought.

Seiger (2020) reported that in North Carolina, a Concord pastor was found guilty of stealing more than \$120,000 from a widow who was his family friend in the months following her husband's death. This occurred over 13 months, beginning after her husband died in 2015. It was found that the pastor's suspicious activities were noticed by a relative of the victim and reported to law enforcement. Edem (2021) also reported a widow being sexually involved with the pastor who buried her husband. In Benin City, Edo State, a pastor allegedly turned a widow and her three daughters into his sex slaves, impregnating two of them (Oriental News, 2020). The pastor was also said to have collected every document and property left behind by the twins' late father and claimed that they were sowed to the Church as seed.

These examples represent only a portion of the unethical behaviours pastors may exhibit when caring for and counselling widows. They may subject widows to sexual exploitation, assert control over various aspects of their lives, and assume management of their resources, including finances and property.

Recommendations

According to Babatunde (2021), professionalism in pastoral counselling has gone beyond external qualifications such as training from a seminary or other theological institutions or belonging to one professional body. It involves getting a more comprehensive orientation on issues that border on the smooth and effective dispensation of counsellors' duties. Hence, the following are recommended:

1. Modules on grief dynamics, cultural sensitivity, and ethical considerations for counselling widows should be developed by theological institutions.
2. On different levels, Churches should implement specialised training programmes for pastoral counsellors that focus on the unique challenges widows face. In being proactive, churches should have programmes for married members with a focus on widowhood, ensuring they are prepared and protected after the demise of their partner.

3. Churches should develop clear policies, disseminate these policies, and regularly evaluate their ethical standards to guide pastoral counselling for widows. This will equip pastoral counsellors to perform their duties ethically despite any challenges.
4. There is also a need to advance research on ethical issues in pastoral counselling, as this will contribute significantly to developing guidelines, principles, and best practices to guide pastoral counsellors in navigating complex ethical dilemmas.
5. The pastors should integrate faith, ethics, and professional standards with secular counselling approaches. The pastors, leading the churches should collaborate with professional therapists to refer cases beyond pastoral competencies.
6. It is essential to have client education and empowerment by implementing educational programmes for widows to inform them about their rights, the counselling process and its importance, and the importance of ethical conduct.

Conclusion

Appraising ethical issues in pastoral counselling for widows emphasises the crucial importance of a nuanced and principled approach in supporting this group of people. The unique challenges widows face require a heightened awareness of ethical boundaries and a commitment to upholding the highest standards of care. By acknowledging and addressing these unique challenges through an ethical lens, pastoral counsellors can establish a foundation of trust and support that is essential for widows in their journey toward healing and living a fulfilled life.

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